

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJRM-
695FEBAED0F2B

Published: 2026-01-09

DOI:
<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18197835>

Page No: 28-41

Perceptions of Leadership Styles Within Military Hierarchies: An Appraisal

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Abstract

The leadership of the future is being created now and will mature over the next two decades. Different leadership styles being practised or demonstrated by the military hierarchies must be explored, and the outcomes of the study be utilised for framing the leadership development model. The aim is to explore the perception of leadership style existing in the military hierarchies. A descriptive research design was used in this quantitative study, wherein a total of 71 senior serving defence officers participated.

The attribute of charismatic leadership is predominant among the senior officers, while there is no clear evidence of the overwhelming presence of intellectual stimulation in them. Although a few senior officers have displayed the transactional leadership attribute of management by exception, no one displayed the transactional leadership behaviour of contingent reward. For an organisational culture to become more transformational, top management must articulate the changes that are required.

Index Terms - Performance, Transformational Leadership, Charisma, Transactional Leadership, Organisational Culture

Cite This Paper: Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri (2026). "Perceptions of Leadership Styles Within Military Hierarchies: An Appraisal". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN MANAGEMENT (IJRM)*, vol. 16, no. 1, 2026, pp. 28-41. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18197835>

Introduction

The volatilities and uncertainties of the global security environment raise timely and important questions about the future of humanity's oldest occupation: war (Artur Gruszczak & Sebastian Kaempf, n.d.). A country's existence as an independent entity in the present and future world, its ability to protect its territorial integrity and interests from possible threats, largely depends on its readiness for armed conflicts (Hasanov et al., 2024). Leadership styles play a critical role in maximising military effectiveness (Baboş et al., 2024).

Several theories have been put forward to explain leadership effectiveness. Two of the most prominent leadership theories are Transformational and Transactional leadership theories. Since the late 1980s, theories of transformational and charismatic leadership have been ascendant (George Ogbonna, 2013). Recognising the need for both transformational and transactional leadership in this dynamic environment, researchers are increasingly exploring the full-range leadership model within the military context (Baboş et al., 2024). Transactional and Transformational leadership styles have attracted the interest of many researchers in recent times (George Ogbonna, 2013).

Although most authors agree that Transactional and transformational leadership are different in concept and in practice, many authors believe that transformational leadership significantly augments transactional leadership, resulting in higher levels of individual, group, and organisational performance (Howell & Avolio, 1993, Lowe et al., 1996). Ismail et al., (2010) opined that transformational style relies on social exchange (e.g., follower development) and transactional style is based on economic exchange (e.g., reward contingent job) in managing followers to achieve job targets. Others believe that Transactional leadership is a subset of transformational leadership (*Management-by-Wehrich*, n.d.). According to Bass, (1999) in certain circumstances, leaders can be perceived as having both styles of transformational and transactional practices.

A transformational leader is a person who stimulates and inspires (transforms) followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes (Robbins & Coulter, n.d.) by enhancing the level of motivation, morale, and performance through a variety of mechanisms (George

Ogbonna, 2013). Notwithstanding, Yukl, (1999) identified seven major weaknesses of transformational leadership, viz., ambiguity underlying its influences and processes, or the overemphasis of the theory on leadership processes at the dyadic level, etc.

Whereas transactional leaders give rewards and punishments to encourage performance, making the leader/worker relationship essentially an economic transaction (Bass, 1997). The basis of transactional leadership is the exchange processes between a leader and a follower (Burns, 1978). Transactional leadership encourages specific exchanges and a close connection between goals and rewards. Consequently, workers are not motivated to give anything beyond what is clearly specified in their contract (Bryant, 2003). Transactional leaderships comprise of three components: contingent reward, active management by exception, and passive management by exception (Northouse, n.d.).

(Bass & Avolio Suny-Binghamton, n.d.) suggested that transformational leadership can be taught to people at all levels in an organisation and can also be used in improving team development, decision-making groups, quality initiatives, and reorganisations. Programs designed to develop transformational leadership usually require that leaders or their associates take the MLQ (Bass & Avolio Suny-Binghamton, n.d.) or a similar questionnaire to determine the leader's particular strengths and weaknesses in transformational leadership. Taking the MLQ helps leaders pinpoint areas in which they could improve their leadership (Northouse, n.d.).

Significance of the study

New and emerging technologies are bound to reshape the nature, intensity and composition of all wars to come. But the leadership will remain the single-most important factor in deciding the outcome of any conflict. The leadership development is a continuous process and is best achieved through mentoring. Therefore, it is important to understand the leadership styles of the senior leaders and figure out requirement to carryout changes in the leadership development process.

Literature Review

Transformational Leadership Theory

A transformational leader is a person who stimulates and inspires (transforms) followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes (Robbins & Coulter, n.d.) by enhancing the level of motivation, morale, and performance through a variety of mechanisms (George Ogbonna, 2013). Transformational leaders attempt to raise the consciousness in individuals and to get them to transcend their own self-interests for the sake of others (Northouse, n.d.). Transformational and charismatic leadership theories provide a useful lens for understanding how leaders impact the management of organisational knowledge (Bryant, 2003).

Transformational leaders are active leaders who have four distinguishing characteristics: charisma, inspiration, intellectual stimulation and individualised consideration (Bass, 1999). Charisma is the extent of pride, faith and respect leaders encourage their workers to have in themselves, their leaders and their organisations. Inspiration is the ability to motivate followers largely through the communication of high expectations. Intellectual stimulation is the frequency with which leaders encourage employees to be innovative in their problem-solving and solutions. Finally, individualised consideration is the degree of personal attention and encouragement of self-development a leader imparts to the employees. Transformational leaders devote significant energy to leading and respect the gifts and abilities of their workers (Bryant, 2003). Transformational leadership is fundamentally morally uplifting (Howell & Avolio, 1993). This emphasis sets the transformational approach apart from all other approaches to leadership because it suggests that leadership has a moral dimension (Northouse, n.d.).

Transactional Leadership Factors

Bass (1985) found that transformational leadership consisted of three factors: *charismatic leadership (CL)*, *intellectual stimulation (IS)* and *individual consideration (IC)*.

Charismatic Leadership (CL). According to (Bass, 1999) charismatic leadership (idealised influence) is the dimension characterised by making others feel good, making

others proud to be associated with the leader, and earning faith from the subordinate. It is the emotional component of leadership (Day & Antonakis, 2012a). Idealised influence describes leaders who act as strong role models for followers; followers identify with these leaders and want very much to emulate them. These leaders usually have very high standards of moral and ethical conduct and can be counted on to do the right thing. They are deeply respected by followers, who usually place a great deal of trust in them. They provide followers with a vision and a sense of mission (Northouse, n.d.).

Intellectual Stimulation (IS). Bass (1999) noted that this dimension is characterised by the leader's ability to make others think about new ways of performing work, new ways of looking at work, and to be creative in their own problem-solving methods. It includes leadership that stimulates followers to be creative and innovative and to challenge their own beliefs and values, as well as those of the leader and the organisation (Northouse, n.d.).

Individual Consideration (IC). Bass (1999) noted that this dimension is characterised by how well the leader encourages individuals to develop themselves, how much feedback the leader thinks he or she gives to subordinates, and how well the leader takes time to bring workers into the team or the group. This factor is representative of leaders who provide a supportive climate in which they listen carefully to the individual needs of followers. Leaders act as coaches and advisers while trying to assist followers in becoming fully actualised (Northouse, n.d.).

Transactional Leadership Theory

Bass, (1999) contrasts transformational leaders with transactional leaders, and Conger & Kanungo (1998) contrast charismatic leaders with non-charismatic leaders. While transformational leaders inspire exceptional performance, transactional or non-charismatic leaders aspire to achieve solid, consistent performance that meets agreed upon goals (Bryant, 2003). Transactional leaders have three primary characteristics. First, transactional leaders work with their team members to develop clear, specific goals and ensure that workers get the reward promised for meeting the goals. Second, they exchange rewards and promises of rewards for worker effort. Finally, transactional leaders are responsive to the immediate self-

interests of workers if their needs can be met while getting the work done (Bryant, 2003).

Transactional Leadership Factors

Transactional leadership differs from transformational leadership in that the transactional leader does not individualise the needs of followers or focus on their personal development (Northouse, n.d.).

Contingent Reward (CR). Here, the leader clarifies what is expected from followers and what they will receive if they meet the expected levels of performance (Bass & Avolio Suny-Binghamton, n.d.). It is an exchange process between leaders and followers in which effort by followers is exchanged for specified rewards. With this kind of leadership, the leader tries to obtain agreement from followers on what must be done and what the payoffs will be for the people doing it (Northouse, n.d.).

Management by Exception (ME). It is leadership that involves corrective criticism, negative feedback, and negative reinforcement. Management-by-exception takes two forms: active and passive (Northouse, n.d.).

Active Management by Exception. In this, the leader focuses on monitoring task execution for any problems that might arise and correcting those problems to maintain current performance levels.

Passive Avoidant Leadership. Here, the leader tends to react only after problems have become serious to take corrective action, and often avoids making any decisions at all.

Leadership as a single continuum

In his approach, Bass extended Burns's work by giving more attention to followers' rather than leaders' needs, by suggesting that transformational leadership could apply to situations in which the outcomes were not positive, and by describing transactional and transformational leadership as a single continuum (Figure 1) rather than mutually independent continua (Northouse, n.d.)

Figure 1: Leadership Continuum from Transformational to Laissez-Faire Leadership
(Source: Leadership: Theory and Practice, Seventh Edition by Peter G. Northouse)

Research Methodology

Research aim

This research aimed to explore the perception of leadership style existing in the military hierarchies

Participants

The participants of this study were 71 senior military officers of the Indian Defence Forces.

Instrument

(Bass & Avolio Suny-Binghamton, n.d.) suggested that transformational leadership can be taught to people at all levels in an organisation and can also be used in improving team development, decision-making groups, quality initiatives, and reorganisations (Bass, 1995). Programs designed to develop transformational leadership usually require that leaders or their associates take the MLQ (Bass & Avolio Suny-Binghamton, n.d.) or a similar questionnaire to determine the leader's particular strengths and weaknesses in transformational leadership.

Taking the MLQ helps leaders pinpoint areas in which they could improve their leadership. For example, leaders might learn that it would be beneficial if they were more confident in expressing their goals, or that they need to spend more time nurturing followers, or that they need to be more tolerant of opposing viewpoints. The MLQ is the springboard to helping leaders improve a whole series of their leadership attributes (Northouse, n.d.)

This study employed the widely used 10-item subset of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) Form 1 that defined transactional and transformational factors in Bass's (1985) first-order exploratory analysis. The Questionnaire, used in this research, has 7 transformational leadership items - 3 for Charismatic Leadership (CL), 2 for Intellectual Stimulation (IS), and 2 for Individualised Consideration (IC). It has 3 transactional leadership items - 1 for Contingent Reward (CR) and 2 for Management-by-Exception (ME). The 10-item questionnaire is as follows: -

E1	He was a role model for me to follow.	CL
E2	He made me feel that we could reach our goals even without him if we had to.	IC
E3	He was an inspiration to all the units of the formation.	CL
E4	He used to give personalised attention to troops, who seemed neglected (viz., tradesmen).	IC
E5	He used to talk a lot about honours and awards and requirement to work for them.	CR
E6	His ideas forced me to rethink some of my own ideas that I had never questioned before.	IS
E7	He used to encourage me to express my ideas and opinions in a free and frank manner.	CL
E8	He used to let me continue doing my job in the same way I was doing earlier.	ME
E9	As long as things were going right, he never tried to change anything.	ME
E10	He provided me with new ways of looking at things, which used to be difficult for me.	IS

The above statements pertained to the demonstrated leadership components of our seniors, while we were on our respective command assignments. A different five-point scale (1 = Not at all; 2 = Once in a while; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Fairly often; 5 = Frequently, if not always) was used for this section.

Data Analysis and Results

The results of the study were as follows: The measurement of outcome variables and their correlations are given below: -

Descriptive Statistics.

	<i>E 1</i>	<i>E2</i>	<i>E3</i>	<i>E4</i>	<i>E5</i>	<i>E6</i>	<i>E7</i>	<i>E8</i>	<i>E9</i>	<i>E10</i>
Mean	3.509	3.236	3.436	3.34	2.327	3.000	3.78	3.34	3.473	3.000
Std Error	0.129	0.135	0.12	0.13	0.16	0.162	0.13	0.14	0.121	0.137
Median	4.000	3.000	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.000	4.00	4.00	3.000	3.000
Mode	4.000	4.000	3.00	4.00	2.00	3.000	4.00	4.00	3.000	3.000
Std Deviation	0.960	0.999	0.91	1.02	1.24	1.202	1.03	1.07	0.900	1.018
Sample Variance	0.921	0.999	0.84	1.04	1.55	1.444	1.06	1.15	0.809	1.037
Kurtosis	0.297	-0.235	-0.10	-0.09	-0.22	-	-0.40	-	0.035	-0.249
						0.615		0.18		
Skewness	-0.54	-0.384	-0.10	-0.42	0.825	-	-0.48	-	-0.153	0.000
						0.199		0.55		

Correlation Matrix.

	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10
E 1	1.000									
E 2	0.509	1.000								
E 3	0.731	0.612	1.000							
E 4	0.516	0.444	0.586	1.000						
E 5	-0.26	-0.27	-0.353	-0.33	1.000					
E 6	0.530	0.262	0.571	0.392	0.012	1.000				
E 7	0.395	0.482	0.552	0.547	-0.303	0.314	1.000			
E 8	0.275	0.353	0.332	0.344	-0.224	0.072	0.520	1.000		
E 9	-0.11	0.100	-0.097	0.222	0.041	-0.06	0.113	0.498	1.000	
E 10	0.398	0.309	0.416	0.391	0.015	0.560	0.459	0.338	0.202	1.000

Analysis

The attribute of Charismatic Leadership (CR) is predominant among the senior officers (E1, E3 and E7).

On the attribute of Intellectual Stimulation (IS), there is no clear evidence of their overwhelming presence in our senior officers (E6 and E10). Intellectual stimulation is displayed when the leader helps followers to become more innovative and creative.

Senior officers have also displayed the transactional leadership attribute of Management by Exception (E8 and E9). In active management-by-exception, the leader monitors the follower's performance and takes corrective action if the follower fails to meet standards, or it may take the form of passive leadership, in which the leader practices passive management-by-exception by waiting for problems to arise before taking corrective action or is laissez-faire and avoids taking any action.

It is also evident that the senior officers have not displayed transactional leadership behaviour of Contingent Reward (CR) (E5), in which the leader clarifies for the follower, through direction or participation, what the follower needs to do to be rewarded for the effort.

The full range of leadership, as measured by the MLQ, implies that every leader displays a frequency of both the transactional and transformational factors. Leaders who are more satisfying to their followers and more effective as leaders tend to be more transformational and less transactional (Avolio & Bass, 1991).

Correlation has been established between E1 and E3, as also between E2 and E3. The three basic transformational dimensions, i.e., individualised consideration, intellectual stimulation, and idealised influence (charisma), are strongly correlated with each other as shown above.

Discussion

Pinpointing the ideal leadership style for the military, especially for frontline leaders balancing the demands of superiors and subordinates, can be difficult (Baboş et al., 2024). Transformational leadership is an effective form of leadership globally because the transformational leaders are consistent with their vision and are more careful about their followers (Hossain Reza, n.d.). Transformational leadership is prevalent and expected at the senior hierarchical levels. Both transformational leaders and charismatic leaders gain influence by demonstrating important personal characteristics (Kuhnert & Lewis, 1987). All organisations, therefore, should invest in developing transformational leadership that will help in leveraging the human capital for achieving organisational effectiveness.

Transformational and transactional leadership are affected by moral and personal development, training and education. Mature moral development is required of the transformational leader (Kuhnert & Lewis, 1987). One's parents' moral standards and one's leadership experiences in school and extracurricular activities forecast subsequent tendencies to be more transformational as adult leaders (Day & Antonakis, 2012b). Bass states that transformational leadership qualities are affected by individuals' childhood experiences. Transformational leaders described childhood and adolescent experiences with caring but challenging parents who held high standards. Schools also made a difference, as did work

experiences as a young adult (Bass & Avolio Suny-Binghamton, n.d.). Therefore, transformational leaders have distinct personality attributes that are different from those characterising their transactional counterparts. For an organisational culture to become more transformational, top management must articulate the changes that are required. Desired role models of leadership begin at the top and are encouraged at each successive level below. The behaviours of top-level leaders become symbols of the organisation's new culture.

Conclusion

Military leadership in the 21st century will likely be characterised by collaboration and cooperation as much as it is by direction and decision. In addition to leading soldiers, we will operate by, with, and through people and organisations outside the military. Therefore, military leaders must recognise that there are different cultures of leadership, know how to adjust their own styles and approaches to accommodate those views, and be comfortable working within and around other-than-military organisations.

(Day & Antonakis, 2012b) posited that by linking together leader individual differences, leader styles, and leader outcomes, one will ensure not only the correct estimation of endogenous variables, but also provide us with a better understanding of the importance of leadership. Transformational leadership theory provides one way to enhance our understanding of team performance (Dionne et al., 2004).

Military leadership philosophy should reflect the future vision, describing what leadership should be to meet the future demands, rather than reasserting what the leadership has been in the past. The concept of leadership has to be understood for its multifaceted and symbiotic nature. It can no longer be thought of as a distinct or concise subject. It is much more than simply the interaction between the leader and the led, and it relies on much more than the attributes and competencies of the leader to be effective.

All organisations should conduct a thorough reassessment of their leadership philosophy to ensure we have appropriately defined leadership and leader development within our organisation and have planned, resourced, and implemented systems to encourage that leadership philosophy throughout the Army. This reassessment should be ruthless in its scepticism, rigorous in its objectivity, and it should strive for multiple perspectives. Rather than

rely on a command relationship that makes our system work or imposes our own cultural norms upon others, we might just need to better understand leadership in a purer sense and practice, simply, Leadership!

Acknowledgement

Each participant in the study was acknowledged for their time, voluntary contribution and active participation.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The researcher declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the authorship and/or publication of this article.

Consent

Necessary consent from the participants was obtained for undertaking the study. Participation in this study was completely voluntary.

Funding

This study received no financial support.

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